

Enabling Data Sovereignty through Trusted Research Environments in European Data Spaces

Highlights from the EOSC-ENTRUST online workshop held on 25 February 2026

Executive summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST project held an online workshop on 25 February 2026 for EOSC and Data Space stakeholders on data sovereignty and Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Around 70 experts joined the workshop to listen to presentations from the project, EOSC Association, BioMedIT, HDR UK, the BSC AI Factory, and the Language Data Space. Presentations covered current challenges, national perspectives, and technical developments related to data sovereignty and cross-border access to sensitive data.

The workshop included a panel discussion that explored user diversity, TRE roles in Data Spaces, resource-intensive workflows, and future expectations for sensitive-data research. Speakers recognized that TREs are essential for data sovereignty, but interoperability is still a core challenge. The workshop highlighted the need for a federated European TRE ecosystem supported by aligned governance, shared standards, and the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint.

Introduction

The demand for secure, interoperable access to sensitive data is rapidly increasing. Research in fields such as health, genomics, and social sciences relies heavily on data that cannot be openly shared due to legal, ethical, or privacy constraints. At the same time, new European Data Spaces and the evolving EOSC Federation are raising expectations for cross-border collaboration and responsible data reuse. These initiatives promise scientific and societal benefits, but they also expose persistent challenges: fragmented national legislation, varying maturity levels of secure data environments, and a lack of common operational and technical standards. Together, these create a landscape where organisations want to collaborate, but lack trusted and harmonised mechanisms for doing so safely and efficiently.

A key solution for providing interoperability are Trusted Research Environments (TREs) that are secure platforms that allow controlled analysis of sensitive data. However, TREs differ widely in design, governance, and capabilities across countries and sectors. To address these gaps, the EOSC-ENTRUST project aims to develop a European network of TREs and a common blueprint for federated, secure data access, enabling cross border analysis of sensitive data while meeting legal, ethical, and technical requirements.

On 25 February 2026, EOSC-ENTRUST held its outreach workshop “Enabling Data Sovereignty through Trusted Research Environments in European Data Spaces.” The event gathered EOSC stakeholders, TRE providers, Data Space initiatives, and researchers to discuss how TREs can support future Data Spaces and the EOSC Federation. The event served as a platform for aligning perspectives, sharing practical experiences, and identifying future directions for building an interoperable European data landscape.

Around 70 experts joined the workshop to follow presentations from the EOSC-ENTRUST project, EOSC Association, BioMedIT, HDR UK, the BSC AI Factory, and the Language Data Space. Presentations were followed by a panel discussion on topical issues around TREs and Data Spaces, and how TREs can support the next generation of European Data Spaces.

Agenda for the session

Date: 25 February 2026 | Time: 11:00-12:30 CET | Online

Time	Agenda
11:00	Welcome from the moderator Speaker: Per Öster
11:00-11:10	Introduction from the EOSC-ENTRUST project Speaker: Jonathan Tedds
11:10-12:00	Current issues on data sovereignty from the panellists <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC (Speaker: Bob Jones) • BioMedIT (Speaker: Davide Chiarugi) • HDR UK (Speaker: Emily Jefferson) • BSC AI Factory (Speaker: Salvador Capella Gutierrez) • Language Data Space (Speaker: Martin Matthiesen)
12:00-12:30	Panel discussion and Q&A
12:30	Closing remarks Speaker: Per Öster

Key takeaways from the presentations

Speakers provided insight into the challenges and opportunities shaping sensitive data access in Europe today. Presentations emphasised the increasing need for secure processing environments as Data Spaces mature, and the importance of aligning national regulations, technical infrastructures, and governance frameworks to support European interoperability.

Introduction from the EOSC-ENTRUST project – Jonathan Tedds

Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR / EOSC-ENTRUST) opened the workshop with an overview of EOSC-ENTRUST's mission: to build a European network of TREs and develop a blueprint for federated data access and analysis. He defined data sovereignty in the European context and explained how TREs provide a controlled and auditable environment for sensitive data. His presentation introduced the project's approach to aligning TRE providers, unifying terminology, and enabling cross-border trusted research across Europe.

An introduction to the EOSC Federation – Bob Jones

Bob Jones (CERN / EOSC Association), introduced the EOSC Federation as the infrastructure enabling European researchers to store, share, analyse, and reuse FAIR research outputs across borders. The federation model addresses challenges around security, governance, and interoperability by combining existing infrastructures into a system of systems guided by principles of trust, inclusivity, autonomy, and low barriers to entry.

Bob's presentation highlighted security and governance challenges associated with cross border research data sharing. EOSC addresses these through a federation model that ensures compliance with European regulations, enforces strong authentication and data quality controls, and provides a secure virtual collaboration environment. He outlined core principles underpinning the EOSC Federation, such as building on existing infrastructures, ensuring inclusivity and low barriers to entry, maintaining institutional autonomy, promoting transparency, and embedding trust and security at all levels.

Bob demonstrated real multi-node scientific use cases, including AI enabled discovery tools, environmental data workflows, pathogen genomics, and physics data processing, which illustrate how the federation supports diverse research needs. The presentation also included examples of EOSC Federation Nodes and outlined key services offered through the EOSC EU Node, along with the updated EOSC Federation Handbook.

BioMedIT: Switzerland's Trusted Research Environment – Davide Chiarugi

Davide Chiarugi (BioMedIT) presented Switzerland's national federated Trusted Research Environment (fTRE), which has been established to address the growing challenges of conducting research on sensitive health data. The Swiss health ecosystem generates large volumes of sensitive information, but research is often hindered by strict privacy

requirements, complex regulatory obligations, and interoperability issues across institutions. BioMedIT tackles these barriers by coordinating secure processing environments, authentication and access management, data-transfer mechanisms, and shared tools that support compliant multi-institutional research.

As a national infrastructure, BioMedIT provides a secure cloud and HPC environment built on “security by design” principles and a common Swiss information-security policy. It operates three university-based nodes, a central portal managed by SIB, and B-spaces (dedicated secure workspaces for research projects). BioMedIT’s TRE model enables large-scale, sensitive data research with more than 120 projects, over 1,000 users, 33 data providers, and substantial computational capacity.

Current issues with data sovereignty in the UK – Emily Jefferson

Emily Jefferson (Health Data Research UK) presented HDR UK’s mission to accelerate trustworthy data use by improving how researchers find, access, link, curate, and analyse sensitive data. The UK TRE landscape is rapidly expanding across health, governmental, academic, and industrial sectors, but remains governed by complex legal frameworks involving GDPR alignment, the Common Law Duty of Confidentiality, devolved nation specific data controllers, and strict rules for unconsented health data movement. Nonetheless, the long term vision is for sensitive data to be used as efficiently and safely as open data, enabling transformative advances in clinical, biomedical, and public health research.

Emily’s presentation highlighted the rise of TRE networks and the increasing need for federation models, supported by standards such as SATRE, OMOP, and the 5 Safes. UK investments like the Health Data Research Service and the National Data Library aim to streamline access, while alignment with EOSC-ENTRUST and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) is becoming increasingly important for cross border sensitive data research.

Perspectives on TREs and BSC AI Factory – Salvador Capella-Gutierrez

The BSC AI Factory, part of the EuroHPC AI Factories initiative, aims to reduce barriers to AI innovation by offering HPC capacity, technical expertise, industry focused services, and workforce training. Its “openVRE” platform (a Virtual Research Environment) provides an integrated environment for workflows, authentication, metadata, tools, storage, and compute resources.

Salva Capella-Gutierrez (BSC AI Factory) described the transition from openVRE to safeVRE, designed to meet stricter EU requirements for sensitive data by incorporating tiered trust models, 5 Safes principles, policy as code, airlock mechanisms, privacy by design, and data/model sovereignty. Inspired by the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint, the roadmap moves from ISO 27001 certified ad hoc solutions to a cloud based TRE and finally an HPC TRE integrated with MareNostrum 5. This multi-stage strategy reflects BSC’s goal of

building cross cutting TRE capabilities that can support researchers, clinicians, industry partners, and regulatory demands in a harmonized, scalable manner.

Language Data Spaces – Martin Matthiesen

Martin Matthiesen (CSC) presented the Language Data Space (LDS) and provided an overview of Data Spaces and their governance, noting that although many Data Spaces are announced, few are truly operational. The LDS is a European Commission -funded initiative that is currently in testing and offers a catalogue, metadata tools, exchange protocols, licensing frameworks, logging and analytics, and monitoring. Machine readable contracts support automated negotiation and auditing.

Martin described the current adoption landscape and future outlook of the LDS. In academia, federated identity systems like eduGAIN make LDS integration straightforward, though existing infrastructures (e.g., CLARIN) already meet many needs. In industry, adoption remains slower due to the absence of established identity management systems and the resources required to maintain LDS connectors. Looking ahead, the LDS may serve as a promising model for data sharing, but is currently better suited to less sensitive data, as it lacks Encryption at Rest support. The platform is expected to be taken over by ALT EDIC, yet uptake by institutions remains uncertain. TREs could help encourage adoption, if the administrative burden for providers remains realistic.

Panel discussion highlights

The concluding panel explored four central questions.

How do we attract and support a diverse range of users, including those from smaller countries, institutions, or communities, to actively participate in a federated TRE ecosystem?

Panelists noted that this needs to be a sustainable practice. Sustainability depends not only on technology but also on trust, governance, funding, and relationships. Governance remains the primary bottleneck, requiring alignment before technical federations can succeed. Examples such as the Norwegian National Library show that legal restrictions can be managed with appropriate safeguards.

How do TREs fit into the emerging European Data Spaces — are they infrastructure, governance tools, or both?

TREs were seen as key enablers for Data Spaces, though more features may be needed to build trust, especially for industry. Agreements like the UK Biobank-AstraZeneca model illustrate how negotiated benefits can make data sharing viable. EOSC ENTRUST's common language and blueprint aim to lower barriers to adoption across Data Spaces.

What are the challenges you see in using resource intensive workflows (e.g. AI methods) with sensitive data in TREs, and do current TRE models need to evolve to address them?

Cross-border access to HPC resources raises questions around reciprocity and value exchange. Security often reduces computational efficiency, demanding careful balance. While federated learning is promising, it requires strong local capacity and governance for models leaving the secure environment.

If we reconvene in five years, what would you hope has fundamentally changed for researchers working with sensitive data in Europe?

Panelists hope for pragmatic, risk aligned security models, legal harmonization, and a stronger EOSC foundation capable of supporting sensitive data at scale.

Conclusions

The workshop highlighted a shared, European ambition: enabling secure, governed, interoperable access to sensitive data for high-impact research. Achieving this vision will require harmonised governance frameworks, interoperable TRE capabilities, and deeper collaboration across TRE providers, Data Space initiatives, and EOSC stakeholders. EOSC-ENTRUST is well-positioned to support this transformation through its blueprint, TRE network, and collaboration across Data Spaces, infrastructures, and communities.